

Comprehensive approach to the implementation of an effective system and mechanism for managing economic security at enterprises in times of national economic revival

The subject of the research is the theoretical and methodological approaches to implementing an effective system and mechanism for managing economic security at enterprises under conditions of Ukraine's economic recovery.

The purpose of the study is to substantiate the methodological and applied principles of implementing an effective system and mechanism for managing economic security at enterprises under conditions of national economic recovery.

Research methods. During the writing of the article, a number of general scientific research methods were used: methods of analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, dialectical method of cognition, complex approach, methods of comparisons and analogies, logical generalization, scientific abstraction, hypothetical method, observation, measurement, tabular and graphical methods.

Presentation of the main material (research results). The article considers the system of economic security in the context of one of the components of the enterprise's integrated security system. The system of group and individual indicators of the enterprise's economic security is proposed to determine the integral indicator (level of economic security) on the appropriate scale. The author's interpretation of the category «enterprise's economic security management mechanism» is proposed as a set of general and special methods, means, tools, levers, functions and principles of organizational, managerial and economic activities of the enterprise based on compliance with legislative norms and use of the necessary information with a view to ensuring an appropriate level of economic security and protection of vital economic interests. The author's own version of the enterprise's economic security management mechanism with structural elements was developed, which allowed coordinating the process of organizing the economic security system with sequential actions and stages. At the conceptual level, a mechanism of interaction between the functional components of the enterprise's economic security system is identified. The expediency of creating integrated security services at enterprises is substantiated, which in the future will consist of specialized divisions (sectors and groups). The typical internal structure of a security service in a strategic perspective is considered, which will include: the Head of the Service, the Head of the Protection Sector (together with Security Guards) and the Economic Security Inspector (together with a Programmer and a Database Specialist).

Field of application of results. The results of the study can be used in the practical activities of a modern enterprise to improve the security subsystem in forming a holistic system for managing enterprise's economic security under conditions of transformational changes.

Conclusions on the article. In the course of the work, the following scientific results were obtained: the system of group and individual indicators of enterprise's economic security to determine the integral indicator on the appropriate scale was proposed, the author's own version of enterprise's economic security management mechanism with structural elements was developed, the mechanism of interaction of functional components of the enterprise's economic security system is identified, and a typical internal structure of the security service in the strategic perspective is considered.

Keywords: enterprise security, economic security, the enterprise's economic security system, the enterprise's economic security management mechanism, functional components of the economic security system, security service, comprehensive approach, recovery economy.

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Комплексний підхід до впровадження ефективної системи та механізму управління економічною безпекою на підприємствах у період відродження національної економіки

Предметом дослідження є теоретико-методичні підходи до впровадження ефективної систе-

ми та механізму управління економічною безпекою на підприємствах в умовах відновлення економіки України.

Метою дослідження є обґрунтування методологічних та прикладних засад впровадження ефективної системи та механізму управління економічною безпекою на підприємствах в умовах відновлення національної економіки.

Методи дослідження. Під час написання статті використано низку загальнонаукових методів дослідження: методи аналізу та синтезу, індукції та дедукції, діалектичний метод пізнання, комплексний підхід, методи порівнянь і аналогій, логічного узагальнення, наукового абстрагування, гіпотетичний метод, спостереження, вимірювання, табличний і графічний методи.

Презентація основного матеріалу (результати дослідження). У статті розглянуто систему економічної безпеки у контексті однієї зі складових комплексної системи безпеки підприємства. Запропоновано систему групових та одиничних показників економічної безпеки підприємства для визначення інтегрального показника (рівня економічної безпеки) за відповідною шкалою. Подано авторське трактування категорії «механізм управління економічною безпекою підприємства» як сукупність загальних і спеціальних методів, засобів, інструментів, важелів, функцій та принципів організаційної, управлінської, економічної діяльності підприємства на основі дотримання законодавчих норм та використання необхідної інформації з метою забезпечення належного рівня економічної безпеки і захисту життєво важливих економічних інтересів. Розроблено авторський варіант механізму управління економічною безпекою підприємства зі структурними елементами, що дозволило узгодити процес організації системи економічної безпеки із послідовними діями та етапами. На концептуальному рівні виділено механізм взаємодії функціональних складових системи економічної безпеки підприємства. Обґрунтовано доцільність створення на підприємствах цілісних служб безпеки, що складатимуться у перспективі зі спеціалізованих підрозділів (секторів і груп). Розглянуто типову внутрішню структуру служби безпеки у стратегічній перспективі, до складу якої входять: начальник служби, начальник сектору охорони (разом з охоронцями) та інспектор з економічної безпеки (разом з програмістом та фахівцем баз даних).

Галузь застосування результатів. Результати дослідження можуть бути використані у практичній діяльності сучасного підприємства для удосконалення підсистеми безпеки при формуванні цілісної системи управління економічною безпекою підприємства в умовах трансформаційних змін.

Висновки за статтею. У процесі виконання роботи було отримано наступні наукові результати: запропоновано систему групових та одиничних показників економічної безпеки підприємства для визначення інтегрального показника за відповідною шкалою, розроблено авторський варіант механізму управління економічною безпекою підприємства зі структурними елементами, а також виділено механізм взаємодії функціональних складових системи економічної безпеки підприємства та розглянуто типову внутрішню структуру служби безпеки у стратегічній перспективі.

Ключові слова: безпека підприємства, економічна безпека, система економічної безпеки підприємства, механізм управління економічною безпекою підприємства, функціональні складові системи економічної безпеки, служба безпеки, комплексний підхід, економіка відновлення.

Formulation of the problem in general. The functioning of the national economy in the period of severe shocks caused by the ongoing hostilities in the vast majority of our country's territory and the need to develop effective measures to quickly recover the former potential of market structures brings to the fore the issue of enterprise's economic security as holistic socio-economic systems. In such circumstances, it is the formation of an effective economic security management system at enterprises with appropriate processes

and management mechanisms that will be a key condition for ensuring their development potential and sustainable competitive advantages.

Under conditions of transformational changes, the vast majority of Ukrainian enterprises are forced to look for reliable means of protection against the destruction of their main production facilities, to relocate equipment and employees, and to provide insurance of material assets to compensate for the losses incurred, which will at least ensure normal conditions for business operation and simple reproduction of

fixed capital. In this connection, the management of business enterprises is increasingly paying attention to ensuring the security of economic activity through the formation and implementation of effective systems of their economic security.

The need to develop and implement an effective system and mechanism for managing economic security at enterprises of various forms of ownership and sectoral subordination during wartime and post-war economic recovery in Ukraine is an urgent scientific problem, the successful solution of which determines the future of the state's economic system. Given the existence of a number of risks and threats to the competitive environment, the lack of adaptive development programs and market behavior strategies, top managers of enterprises need to start the process of forming the economic security management system that will be suitable for operation in a recovery economy.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The problems of developing and implementing an effective system of economic security at the macro and micro levels have been the field of research interests of leading scientists in the sphere of security studies, among whom it is appropriate to single out: O. V. Cherevko, O. I. Chernyak, V. M. Geets, O. L. Gerasymova, O. L. Korobchynskyi, G. V. Kozachenko, M. O. Kyzym, O. M. Lyashenko, N. Matviychuk, V. I. Meyta, V. P. Ponomaryov, O. O. Sosnovska, O. V. Vasyliiev, Z. B. Zhyvko and others [1, 5, 6, 8].

Certain theoretical and methodological aspects of the study of the enterprise economic security are devoted to publications by V. S. Dombrovskyi, I. O. Dotsenko, S. V. Kovalenko, R. S. Kvasnytska, O. L. Plastun, A. O. Yepifanov, V. V. Zaychenko [2, 3, 4, 10].

Considerable attention to determining the content of enterprise's economic security management mechanism is paid by N. Ye. Hryshko, T. B. Ignashkina, O. I. Maslak, S. V. Saloyid, A. L. Shatokhin [7, 9, 11]. The characteristics of the main components of the subsystems of the general system of enterprise's economic security and the process of evaluating its effectiveness on the basis of the resource-functional approach are given in the author's work [12].

However, while paying tribute to the existing scientific works on economic security, management science still has some unresolved issues of forming a holistic system of economic security management at business enterprises and implementing

effective mechanisms for economic security management at enterprises in various sectors of the national economy.

Forming the goals of the article. The purpose of the study is to substantiate the methodological and applied principles of implementing an effective system and mechanism for managing economic security at enterprises under conditions of national economic recovery.

In accordance with the purpose of the study, the system of group and individual indicators of enterprise's economic security to determine the integral indicator on the appropriate scale was proposed, the author's own version of enterprise's economic security management mechanism with structural elements was developed, the mechanism of interaction of functional components of the enterprise's economic security system is identified, and a typical internal structure of the security service in the strategic perspective is considered.

Formulation of the main material. In the conditions of market transformations, the role and importance of economic security of enterprises as a factor of their sustainable development has increased. That is why it is advisable to consider the basic concept of economic security.

In their monographic study, A. O. Yepifanov, O. L. Plastun and V. S. Dombrovskyi note that «in general, economic security is a qualitative characteristic of an economic system that determines its ability to support normal conditions of the system's performance, development within the framework of the goals set for the system, and in cases of various threats (external and internal), the system should be able to withstand them and restore its own performance» [10, p. 11, 18].

Scientist I. O. Dotsenko considers the concept of «enterprise's economic security» as «the state of security of the enterprise's activities, which is achieved through timely detection, prevention, neutralization of real and potential risks, characterized by stable functioning and sustainable development of the enterprise in the future» [2, p. 74].

A similar statement is supported by V. V. Zaychenko and S. V. Kovalenko, who propose to understand of the enterprise's economic security as «the state of the enterprise characterized by stability and balance, protection from external and internal threats and their neutralization, ensuring the stable functioning of the enterprise» [3, p. 413].

The level of the enterprise's economic security system depends on how effectively its management and specialists will be able to avoid possible threats and eliminate the harmful effects of certain negative components of the external and internal environment [4, p. 37].

According to the author, the economic security system is one of the components of the integrated security system of the enterprise, which allows combining its economic interests with the demands of the external environment. This system is a crucial component of the general security system, since it influences the formation of competitive advantages, determines the objects of threats and protection within each enterprise.

Representatives of the Ukrainian scientific school G. V. Kozachenko, V. P. Ponomaryov and O. M. Lyashenko note that «...the modern system of economic security management should be flexible, integrated and open, covering principles, techniques and methods, methodologies, procedures, algorithms and models that ensure harmonization of enterprise interests with the interests of the external environment actors interacting with it» [5, Pp. 106–107].

Researchers O. V. Vasyliiev and V. I. Meyta rightly believe that «the enterprise's economic security management system is based on the objects, subjects of the system, goals, objectives, principles and tools of economic security, and the enterprise security service is directly involved in ensuring it» [1, p. 144].

Under the economic security management system, scientist O. L. Korobchynskiy understands «a set of organizational, managerial, technological, technical, preventive and marketing measures aimed at quantitative and qualitative realization of protection of the enterprise's interests from external and internal threats» [6, p. 42].

It should be noted that N. Matviychuk believes that «the integrated system of enterprise's economic security includes the following elements: the purpose, tasks, functions of the security system, principles of its construction and functioning, objects and subjects, and the mechanism of provision» [8, p. 38].

Within the framework of the integrated system of enterprise's economic security, its main functional components are identified, namely: financial, personnel, technical and technological, legal, information, power and environmental security. Each of these components has its own impact on the formation of the enterprise's economic security sys-

tem, which ensures the effective functioning of the management system.

It should be noted that the state of the economic security system should be clearly defined, controlled and timely detected. For this purpose, it should be constantly measured and evaluated using a set of individual and group indicators.

In management science and applied security studies, there are still heated discussions about effective methods for assessing the state of economic security at enterprises in various spheres of economic activity. After analyzing the existing methodological approaches, we recommend the introduction of a system of single indicators of economic security, which are used to calculate group indicators (coefficients characterizing the level of the relevant functional component of the enterprise's economic security system), as shown in Table 1.

According to Table 1, each of the components of the enterprise's economic security system can be characterized by relevant group and individual indicators, which together allow determining the integral indicator – the level of the enterprise's economic security.

Considering that all the identified functional components are equally important for forming the economic security system, we propose to define the general level of enterprise's economic security as the arithmetic mean of the calculated levels of its functional components. The obtained result of the level the enterprise's economic security should be characterized depending on the ranges of values determined in the course of the study in accordance with the Harrington scale (Table 2).

As can be seen from Table 2, the general level of the enterprise's economic security should be assessed in accordance with the Harrington scale. In this case, the value range can be divided into five groups, ranging from an unsatisfactory level (0.00 – 0.19) to an excellent level of the enterprise's economic security (0.80 – 1.00).

By comparing the numerical values of the level of the enterprise's economic security obtained as a result of the calculations, top managers, together with employees of the Financial Department (Financial Manager, Chief Accountant, Financial Analyst, Accountant or Economist), will be able to determine the measures that need to be taken in order to maintain the enterprise's economic security at the existing level or increase the value of

Table 1. Recommended system of group and individual indicators of enterprise's economic security

Integral indicator	Group indicators	Individual indicators
The level of the enterprise's economic security	1. Level of financial security	Absolute liquidity ratio («Acid test»). Autonomy (Economic independence) ratio. Return on total assets (ROA). Return on equity (ROE).
	2. Level of personnel security	Efficiency of the enterprise's human resources management system. The coefficient of stability of the staff. The coefficient of reliability of the staff. Employee labor productivity.
	3. Level of technical and technological security	The degree of depreciation of fixed assets. The degree of serviceability of fixed assets. The share of innovative products in the total volume of products (goods, works, services) sold. Coefficient of mechanization and automation of production processes. Coefficient of the enterprise's innovation activity.
	4. Level of legal security	Legal information security ratio. Share of fines and penalties in total operating expenses. State of legal discipline.
	5. Level of information security	The coefficient of technical protection of information. The coefficient of information completeness. Information accuracy coefficient. Information transmission reliability coefficient.
	6. Level of power security	The efficiency coefficient of protection of the enterprise's property. The degree of physical protection of managers. Coefficient of physical protection of employees. Coefficient of enterprise's protection against illegal penetration.
	7. Level of environmental security	The share of environmental damage in the country's GDP or the region's gross value added. Environmental quality index (environment). Integral indicator of environmental security.

* Source: Developed by the author

this indicator. That is, the presented methodological approach is based on the study of the state of economic security system and the implementation of secure development strategy by the enterprise management.

In order for the enterprise management system to become more effective, it is necessary to consider the management mechanism by which the enterprise's economic security system is formed. That is why it is necessary to focus on characterizing the content of the enterprise's economic security management mechanism.

A fairly general interpretation of the concept of «economic security management mechanism» is given by O. I. Maslak and N. Ye. Hryshko, who noted that «... the economic security management mechanism can be described by means of a scheme whose main parameters describe the content of

management actions, their leading functions and options for possible solutions» [7, p. 200].

From the point of view of researchers A. L. Shatokhin and T. B. Ignashkina, «the enterprise's economic security management mechanism is a system consisting of a management subject and object that use various methods, levers, means, resources to timely solve a set of tasks in order to protect, maintain and improve economic activity in the face of constant changes in the external environment» [11, p. 401].

The scientist S. V. Saloyid believes that «the mechanism for improving the enterprise's economic security involves achieving effective parameters of functioning, preserving production and human potential, and creating a market-type enterprise» [9, p. 254]. However, the proposed definition does not reflect the classical components of the economic security management mechanism.

Table 2. Recommended ranges of values of the level of enterprise’s economic security according to the Harrington scale

Value range	Characteristics of assessing the level of enterprise’s economic security
0,00 – 0,19	Unsatisfactory level of the enterprise’s economic security
0,20 – 0,36	Low level of the enterprise’s economic security
0,37 – 0,62	Satisfactory level of the enterprise’s economic security
0,63 – 0,79	Good level of the enterprise’s economic security
0,80 – 1,00	Excellent level of the enterprise’s economic security

* Source: Summarized and adapted by the author

Given the previous developments of scholars and experts in the field of economic security, the author proposes to understand the mechanism of enterprise economic security management as a set of general and special methods, means, tools, levers, functions and principles of organizational, managerial and economic activities of the enterprise based on compliance with legislative norms and use of the necessary information with a view to ensuring an appropriate level of economic security and protection of vital economic interests.

The purpose of the functioning the economic security management mechanism is to ensure financial and economic balance, achievement of a certain efficiency of activity and set goals and objectives for further enterprise development.

It is worth noting that the enterprise’s economic security management mechanism should include

the following elements: organizational structure of management; functions of organization and management, justification and implementation of effective forms and methods of creating, improving and developing the economic security system; methods of ensuring; means and levers of ensuring; indicators and evaluation criteria; regulatory and information support (Fig. 1).

In accordance with the management mechanism proposed in Fig. 1, the activities of the responsible authorities to ensure the enterprise’s economic security system should include:

- 1) ensuring the sustainability of the enterprise’s economic security;
- 2) continuous monitoring and management of the security system;
- 3) substantiation and implementation of effective forms and methods of creation, improvement

Figure 1. Recommended version of the enterprise’s economic security management mechanism with structural elements

* Source: Developed by the author

and development of the economic security system of the enterprise;

4) comprehensive and effective use of available means of protection of all elements of the production and economic system;

5) constant forecasting of possible threats;

6) appropriate level of professional training of the enterprise's employees.

It should be emphasized that within the framework of the enterprise's economic security management mechanism, the process of organizing the economic security system should be ensured according to the following general scheme of sequential actions and stages:

Stage 1. Analysis of the state of economic security and enterprise's economic diagnostics.

Stage 2. Forming the necessary amount of financial resources.

Stage 3. Forecasting the level of the enterprise's economic security based on the identification of risks and threats from the external environment.

Stage 4. Planning of the enterprise's financial and economic activities by the main groups of indicators.

Stage 5. Operational management of the enterprise's financial and economic activities.

Stage 6. Control over the level of the enterprise's economic security, which involves accounting and cost analysis, as well as audit of financial statements.

Stage 7. Stimulating and encouraging the activities of employees in the performance of production tasks.

Stage 8. General assessment and monitoring the achieved level of the enterprise's economic security.

Moreover, in order to build an effective enterprise's economic security system, it is necessary to:

1) study the specifics of the enterprise's business activities, peculiarities of the market segment occupied, staffing, and thoroughly familiarize yourself with the employees;

2) analyze external and internal threats to the enterprise's security system and study information on crisis situations, their causes and ways to resolve them;

3) audit the available means to ensure the security system and analyze their compliance with the identified threats;

4) model the new enterprise's economic security system by: developing a plan to eliminate the shortcomings identified during the audit; preparing proposals for improving the economic security system (including the creation of the enterprise's security

service or a security system based on it, determining the mechanisms for ensuring economic security and developing an organizational structure for managing the economic security system), calculating all types of necessary resources; planning monthly expenses for ensuring the functioning of the enterprise's economic security system (budget development);

5) approve the model of the new economic security system by a decision of the enterprise's top management and adopt a budget for its maintenance;

6) form the enterprise's economic security system on the basis of the developed management mechanism;

7) assess the efficiency of the formed enterprise's economic security system and identify promising areas for its improvement.

After implementing the measures proposed above, it is advisable to develop and implement the author's version of the mechanism of interaction of the functional components of the economic security system at the level of the enterprise management apparatus (Fig. 2).

The mechanism of interaction of functional components of the enterprise's economic security system proposed in Fig. 2 allows combining linear and functional managers depending on their specialization, while the hierarchical principle of distribution of powers will be observed.

Within the framework of the proposed mechanism, it is advisable to create an integral security service at enterprises, which in the future will consist of specialized divisions (sectors and groups) linked by a common organizational and technological cycle of comprehensive support of the economic security system, a set of tasks and functions to reduce the level or actively counteract all internal and external dangers and threats to the enterprise's economic activity.

The security service in a strategic perspective may include the Head of the Protection Sector (together with Security Guards) and the Economic Security Inspector (together with a Programmer and a Database Specialist). The activity of this structural division will be controlled by the Head of the Security Service, who will report directly to the Deputy General Director (CEO) for general and security issues (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 shows the typical internal structure of the enterprise's security service in a strategic perspective (in 3–5 years from the moment of creation of

Figure 2. Recommended mechanism of interaction of functional components of the enterprise's economic security system

* Source: Developed by the author

Figure 3. Recommended author's version of the typical internal structure of an enterprise's security service in a strategic perspective

* Source: Developed by the author

the structural division). It should be noted that such a structure can be formed depending on the functional needs of the organization of the enterprise's economic security system, its financial capabilities, the number of employees, industry specifics, etc. The author made an attempt to present a schematic image for the perspective structure of the security service, based on the content of the performed tasks and its functional specialization. In each specific case, the internal structure of the security service will have its own design features in accordance with the scope of the functions assigned to it.

For the purpose of clear coordination of work in the context of forming of an effective system of enterprises economic security, it is expedient to create a matrix form of its provision on the basis of existing structural divisions, which will allow the distribution of functions in the system of economic security between different structural divisions, taking into account the presence of relevant specialists in them. This will make it possible to optimize the structure of the security service and effectively use all the enterprise's own resources in creating a holistic system of economic security.

Conclusions

Thus, the formation of the enterprise's economic security system should be carried out on the basis of a comprehensive approach, which involves selecting of its main functional components, the evaluation of these components according to the system of group and individual indicators, implementing of the economic security management mechanism, ensuring the process of organizing the system according to successive actions and stages, and as well as developing of a mechanism for the interaction of the functional components of the economic security system.

In the end, the speed of implementing organizational changes, the effectiveness of the management mechanism, and the integrity of the main components for the general system of Ukrainian enterprises' economic security depend on the available sources and means of realizing the potential of their development under conditions of the wartime economy and postwar recovery.

The implementing of each for the functional components of the enterprises' economic security management system and developing of a holistic organizational and economic mechanism of

economic security management for them remain promising areas of further scientific research.

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